

Using the Profiles Research Networking Software to measure the impact of small research pilot grants

Griffin Weber¹

¹weber@hms.harvard.edu

Department of Biomedical Informatics, Harvard Medical School, Boston (USA)

Introduction

Profiles Research Networking Software (RNS) is a free and open-source web-based expertise search and collaboration tool. It creates online profiles of an organization's investigators by importing lists of names, positions, and contact information from the organization's internal administrative systems. It then searches external data sources to find and link content, such as publications, grants, clinical trials, and more to investigators' profiles (Figure 1). Data mining algorithms analyze the profiles to discover connections between investigators, such as previously co-authoring a publication, doing similar research, or having nearby offices. Data visualizations display these connections as interactive network graphs (Figure 2). Various bibliometric and social network analysis metrics are calculated by the software. The software is available at <https://profiles.catalyst.harvard.edu>.

Figure 2. Interactive investigator network visualizations in Profiles RNS

Figure 1. A Profiles RNS investigator profile.

We originally created Profiles RNS in 2008 at Harvard Medical School to break-down silos in biomedical research and facilitate collaboration. Since then, it has been widely adopted and used in dozens of institutions worldwide, including academic health centers, universities, pharmaceutical companies, and Federal agencies. The websites receive thousands of visitors a day from around the world, and an active developers' community frequently contributes to the software.

Organizations use the data and metrics in Profiles RNS for a wide range of applications. This poster highlights one use case, which is measuring the impact of small research grants, not only on the teams that receive funding, but also on the teams that applied for a grant but were not funded. Specifically, each year, the U.S. National Institutes of Health (NIH) Clinical and Translational Science Award (CTSA) program spends millions of dollars to fund hundreds of small pilot grant projects at academic medical centers across the country. The NIH tracks how many projects were funded and the percent of projects with at least one publication. However, the full impact of pilot grant program is unknown. It is unclear whether these publications would have happened anyway without funding; and, these basic metrics do not address other high priority CTSA goals, such as whether the pilot grants are forming new collaborations or accelerating translation from basic science to clinical practice.

Methods

To better understand the impact of funding in Harvard's CTSA pilot grant program, we developed a method called Random Teams, which matches both funded and unfunded teams to appropriate controls, in order to separate the effects of the pilot grant program from baseline scientific collaboration and productivity. The controls are thousands of "virtual teams" consisting of randomly selected

investigators who did not collaborate on a proposal (Figure 3). Three types of virtual teams were constructed: (1) Regrouped teams contain investigators who applied for funding, but virtually rearranged into new teams. (2) Random teams are randomly selected from all investigators who were eligible to apply for funding, including those who did not apply. (3) Matched teams are randomly selected from all investigators but have individual and team level properties that match actual teams that applied. Characteristics of the virtual collaborations provide null distributions which can be used to statistically test hypotheses about pilot grant funding.

Figure 3. Comparing actual that applied for funding and randomly created “virtual” teams.

Results

We applied our Random Teams approach retrospectively to one year of the CTSA pilot grants at Harvard, using data from Profiles RNS, with a five-year follow-up window. In that year there was a single round of funding, the request for proposals (RFP) did not set any restrictions on the proposal topics, and any Harvard faculty member could apply (37,266 potential applicants in multiple disciplines across 30 Harvard-affiliated schools and institutions). As a result, this provided a unique opportunity to observe an entire research community self-organize into teams. A total of 1,469 investigators assembled into 458 teams that submitted proposals, of which 65 were funded with \$50,000 pilot grants.

Understanding how pilot grant teams formed

We found that teams that applied for funding were more open to new collaborations than they usually are. For example, on average more than 50% of the authors on publications at Harvard have previously been co-authors on another paper, while only 20% of the investigators on pilot grant teams were prior co-authors. Though, compared to random virtual teams, where just 0.02% of member were prior co-authors, the pilot grant teams still needed some prior collaboration as a starting point to bring in new investigators.

Publication impact of the pilot grant program

We found that funded teams published 2.6 articles citing CTSA funding. However, randomly matched teams published 0.9 articles citing the CTSA program. (Some of the random teams might have received a pilot grant in a later year or used other CTSA resources.) Thus, we need to consider this baseline when estimating the added impact of pilot grant funding.

Collaboration impact on teams that were not funded

After five years, funded pilot grant teams, on average, created 2.5 new lasting collaborations (people who co-authored papers together for the first time after receiving funding). However, on average, 1.7 people from the un-funded teams also later published together for the first time, perhaps by eventually receiving funding from some other source. Because there were many more un-funded teams than funded teams, there were actually four times as many new collaborations formed among the un-funded teams than the funded teams.

Discussion and Conclusions

Profiles RNS contains a rich set of data and metrics, not only on individual people, but also on the connections between people, which is important when studying scientific teams. Having comparison teams is critical in understanding the impact of pilot grant funding. We showed how this can provide insights into how pilot grant teams formed and what the added impact of funding was compared to typical patterns of scientific productivity. One of the objectives of pilot grants are to build new collaborations. Surprisingly, the biggest impact the pilot grant program had on collaboration is on the teams that came together to apply for funding but were not awarded grants. Although Profiles RNS is used at many institutions, a limitation of the pilot grant study described here was that it was only conducted at Harvard.

Acknowledgments

This work was funded by NSF awards #1360042 and #1238469 and NIH grants U01GM112623, UL1TR002541, and R01GM137410. Harvard Catalyst, the Weber Lab, Noshir Contractor, and Alina Lungeanu contributed to this project.

References

- Kahlon, M., et al., (2014). The use and significance of a research networking system. *J Med Internet Res.* 2014 Feb 7;16(2):e46.
- Weber, G.M., & Yuan L.A., (2019). The Power of Research Networking Systems to Find Experts and Facilitate Collaboration. Book chapter in *Strategies for Team Science Success* (pp. 541-562). Springer International Publishing.